

Application and use of Social Media Platforms as Predictors of Knowledge Sharing in Federal University Libraries in Nigeria

Dr Medina Mohammed
University Library
Federal University, Dutse, Jigawa – Nigeria

Dr Usman Muhammed Song
Department of Library and Information Sciences
Federal University, Dutse, Jigawa – Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined the use of social media platforms as a predictor of knowledge sharing among librarians in Nigerian academic libraries. The study was guided by objectives to identify the social media platforms used by librarians, determine the extent of their use for knowledge sharing, and examine the predictive influence of social media platform use on enhanced knowledge sharing for service delivery. The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised 601 librarians from 12 selected federal university libraries in Nigeria, and a sample of 240 librarians was determined using the Taro Yamane sample size determination table. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure proportional representation of librarians. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression. The findings revealed that librarians frequently used social networking platforms such as Facebook (71.8%), WhatsApp (67.0%), Pinterest (70.5%), and LinkedIn (48.5%), as well as content-sharing platforms such as YouTube (48.9%), for knowledge sharing. The study also found that social media platforms facilitated the sharing of tacit and explicit knowledge. The regression analysis showed that social media platform types and utilization significantly predicted increased knowledge sharing among librarians for service delivery ($F(3, 117) = 134.998, p = .000, R^2 = 0.776$). The study concluded that social media platforms are significant predictors of knowledge sharing in academic libraries in Nigeria. It is recommended that academic libraries implement social media

policies and provide technological support to enhance knowledge sharing.

Keywords:

Social Media Platforms; Knowledge Sharing; Academic Libraries; Librarians; Library Service Delivery

Background to the Study

The integration of communication platforms into library operations has gained significant attention as libraries seek to adjust to the ever-changing information landscape and meet the needs of contemporary users. Social media has been identified as an enabler for knowledge sharing within organizations. It allows users to easily seek and contribute knowledge, supporting a collaborative environment. The increasing reliance on social media platforms in academic libraries stresses their central role in collaboration and engagement between librarians and users. This paradigm shift presents new opportunities for service delivery and knowledge sharing. Studies by Chore (2023), Okeke and Asifor (2023), and Igbinalola and Olatunde (2023) highlight how these platforms enable seamless sharing of explicit and tacit knowledge, fostering active interactions that redefine the service-delivery landscape. Social media, including platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and YouTube, has become an indispensable tool for disseminating information, promoting library services, and fostering engagement with multiple user groups (Kokab, Arif, & Qaisar, 2023).

In Nigeria, where academic libraries function as critical hubs for research and innovation,

the adoption of social media has attracted increasing attention as a means of meeting the evolving needs of library users. Social media facilitates knowledge sharing and collaboration, but the need for policies to guide their use in university libraries remains critical. Technology integration policies ensure the strategic alignment of social media tools with organizational objectives and optimizing benefits (Chiparausha, Onyancha, & Ezema, 2024). These emerging platforms are now pivotal for professional purposes, enabling rapid exchanges of ideas and best practices among librarians and other stakeholders (Ahmed et al., 2019).

The potential of social media in knowledge sharing has been extensively documented. Platforms like blogs, wikis, and social networks served as mechanisms for knowledge sharing and problem-solving, ultimately improving organizational performance (Kasćelan et al., 2020). Studies by Bhutto, Khoso, and Mehmood (2022) demonstrated a favorable correlation between social media contact and information sharing, emphasizing the role of these tools in fostering organizational learning and innovation. Similarly, Schuster and Kolley (2020) analyzed Twitter's role in diffusing social innovations, revealing insights that could be applied to academic libraries.

Librarians can promote library services, offer virtual reference assistance, and share announcements about new arrivals through social media platforms. Despite these advancements, knowledge gaps exist in the impact of social media on job performance in academic libraries (Usman & Fadhilah, 2020). The challenges of capturing implicit knowledge through social media further complicate its integration into library operations (Kasćelan et al., 2020). There is insufficient understanding of how specific social media platforms influence different facets of library services through knowledge sharing.

Empirical investigations reveal that academic librarians perceive social media tools as both useful and user-friendly for service delivery, particularly in higher education settings (Chiparausha, Onyancha, & Ezema, 2024; Bhutto, Khoso, and Mehmood, 2022). The integration of social media into library operations aligns with the need to adapt to a rapidly evolving information landscape,

ensuring that libraries meet the expectations of modern users. The use of these platforms supports knowledge management (KM) processes by eliminating temporal and spatial barriers, enhancing social interactions, and facilitating the creative application of knowledge (Panahi, Ghalayand, & Sedghi, 2021).

This study aims to reduce these gaps by exploring the types and extent of social media use in facilitating knowledge sharing and enhance library services in Nigerian university libraries. By addressing these issues, the study seeks to provide actionable ways into the systematic integration of social media tools into library practices, contributing to the effective management and dissemination of knowledge in university libraries.

Statement of Problem

Academic libraries play a pivotal role in supporting teaching, learning, and research by providing access to information and fostering the dissemination of knowledge. The advent of digital technologies and the increasing reliance on social media have transformed traditional library practices by creating opportunities for enhanced knowledge sharing and service delivery. Despite the potential of social media platforms, many university libraries, particularly in Nigeria, struggle to fully integrate these tools into their operations.

Empirical studies indicate that while librarians perceive social media as useful and easy to use, there is limited understanding of its impact on job performance and the efficiency of knowledge sharing in Nigerian university libraries (Kokab, Arif & Qaisar, 2023; Chiparausha, Onyancha & Ezema, 2024). Challenges such as the lack of formal social media policies, inadequate technical skills among librarians, limited access to infrastructure, and concerns over data privacy have impeded the effective use of social media for knowledge management. The underutilization of platforms such as wikis and microblogs created a gap in the systematic adoption of social media tools for library services and knowledge sharing (Kasćelan et al., 2020; Ahmed et al., 2019).

Knowledge sharing in academic libraries extends beyond the exchange of information to include the dissemination of tacit knowledge, which is inherently more complex and requires deliberate efforts to capture and share. This

can be effectively done through integrating social media into knowledge management processes. Given the transformative role social media plays in improving library services, addressing these gaps is crucial. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the extent to which social media platforms are utilized for knowledge sharing in Nigerian federal university libraries.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the application and use of social media platforms as correlates of knowledge sharing in federal university libraries in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the social media platforms used by librarians for knowledge sharing in federal university libraries in Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent of social media platforms as predictors of knowledge sharing among librarians in federal university libraries in Nigeria.
3. Determine the challenges affecting the effective use of social media platforms for knowledge sharing in federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

- H1:** There is a significant statistical relationship between the types of social media platforms and knowledge sharing among librarians in federal university libraries in Nigeria.
- H2:** There is a significant statistical relationship between the use of social media platforms and knowledge sharing among librarians in academic libraries in Nigeria.

Literature Review

The use of social media platforms has become increasingly significant for enhancing knowledge sharing in academic libraries, particularly as libraries respond to the changing information needs of students, lecturers, researchers, and other users. Social media platforms are online communication tools that support interaction, collaboration, content creation, information dissemination, and community building. In academic libraries, these platforms are increasingly used to promote library services, share information resources, support reference services, and strengthen engagement between librarians and users (Aslam, R. & Ansari, 2024). According

to Okeke and Asifor (2023), the integration of social media into library practice reflects the need for libraries to adapt to the modern information environment. Similarly, Chiparausha, Onyanha and Ezema (2024) emphasized that although librarians may be prepared to use social media for service delivery, a social media policy is necessary to guide its effective application.

Social media has also been identified as a useful tool for knowledge management and knowledge sharing in academic libraries. Igbnlola and Olatunde (2023) described social media as a communication system that enables the sharing of both explicit and tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge, such as library announcements, electronic resources, database links, e-books, e-journals, and institutional information, can be easily shared on platforms including Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn, blogs, and wikis. Tacit knowledge, which includes professional experience, problem-solving strategies, and best practices among librarians, can also be shared through discussion, collaboration, and online interaction. This supports the view of Mosha and Holmner (2019), who observed that social media platforms create virtual environments that stimulate formal interaction and knowledge-sharing practices among staff. Empirical studies have shown that social media platforms contribute positively to communication, collaboration, and engagement in academic libraries. Chore (2023), Okeke and Asifor (2023), and Igbnlola and Olatunde (2023) noted that social media enhances the relationship between librarians and users by creating interactive channels for information exchange. Chore (2023) identified platforms such as Google Meet, WebEx, Zoom, WhatsApp, Facebook, and Twitter as useful tools for knowledge sharing and information services, including access to databases, e-books, e-journals, e-resources, and web-based reference services. Ahmed et al. (2019) also observed that Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and LinkedIn enable librarians and users to build connections, collaborate, and share knowledge.

The literature further indicates that social media supports the broader knowledge management process in libraries. Chiparausha, Onyanha and Ezema (2024), Igbnlola and Olatunde (2023), Chore (2023), and Panahi,

Ghalavand and Sedghi (2021) argued that emerging information and communication technologies have created new ways of supporting knowledge processes by removing barriers of time and distance. Similarly, Kokab, Arif and Qaisar (2023) maintained that social media improves the creative application of knowledge management by providing a framework for capturing, organizing, and disseminating knowledge. Kasćelan et al. (2020) and Baltova and Baltov (2017) also noted that blogs, microblogs, social networks, and wikis facilitate knowledge management practices and improve organizational performance.

In relation to platform preference, Mladenović and Krajina (2020) found that social networking sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and Twitter, as well as content communities, are more frequently used for knowledge sharing, while blogs and microblogs are less utilized. Schuster and Kolleck (2020) further demonstrated the relevance of Twitter in information dissemination and innovation diffusion, suggesting that similar dynamics may improve academic library services. Panahi, Ghalavand and Sedghi (2021) also emphasized that social media reduces barriers to knowledge sharing and supports problem-solving and decision-making.

Despite these benefits, challenges remain in the effective application of social media for knowledge sharing in academic libraries. Kasćelan et al. (2020) noted that tacit knowledge is difficult to capture because it often exists in the minds of individuals. This makes it necessary for libraries to adopt supportive technologies that can help transform tacit knowledge into explicit and shareable forms. Other challenges include inadequate technological infrastructure, poor internet access, lack of training, limited skills, low motivation, and absence of clear social media policies. Kokab, Arif and Qaisar (2023) identified behavioural intention, knowledge, skills, and enabling technology as important factors that influence social media usage.

In the Nigerian academic library context, the application and use of social media platforms can therefore be seen as important correlates of knowledge sharing. These platforms promote communication, professional collaboration, user engagement, access to information resources, and knowledge

management practices. However, the literature reveals a gap in empirical studies examining how specific social media platforms influence knowledge sharing in academic libraries, especially in Nigeria. Usman and Fadhilah (2020) observed that there is still limited evidence on the impact of social media on job performance in university libraries. Therefore, further research is needed to examine how the systematic use of social media platforms can improve knowledge sharing, service delivery, and organizational performance in Nigerian academic libraries.

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Technology acceptance is becoming a vital part of knowledge management studies. Researchers try to relate technology acceptance to other concepts such as user satisfaction and diffusion of innovation (Welch, Alade & Nichol, 2020; Chao, 2019). This research considered adopting the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology to explain the social media technology usage behaviour in knowledge sharing to predict job performance.

Applying the UTAUT model in this research provides a framework for explaining the role of social media technologies in knowledge sharing. Using the UTAUT model as the theoretical basis to evaluate the influence of technology-related factors on social media adoption for knowledge sharing in libraries will aid in predicting knowledge sharing.

The underlying need of adopting the UTAUT is to foster the use of social media KM technologies for a knowledge-sharing culture within university libraries. The efforts may be directed towards improving skill levels and innovation, and providing them with other resources, such as appropriate IT and data mining training, so that technology adoption becomes an integral part of their daily activities.

Application of UTAUT to the Study

The study adopted two constructs of the UTAUT model: the 'performance expectancy' and the 'social influence' components. The model aims to test whether performance expectancy and social influence components of social media platforms predict behavioural intention to share knowledge for effective service delivery.

Fig. 1: Adapted UTAUT Model for the Study

The underlying need of adopting the UTAUT is to foster the use of IT-supported knowledge sharing platforms within the university libraries under study. Performance expectancy refers to the degree to which librarians believe that using social media will enhance knowledge sharing. Social influence represents the extent to which librarians perceive that important stakeholders (colleagues, supervisors, or institutional policies) encourage them to use social media platforms. Behavioral Intention (BI) depends on whether performance expectancy (social media platforms) and social influence (enhanced by social satisfaction) predict intention to use the platforms for knowledge sharing. The study examines whether these factors influence librarians' willingness to use technologies for knowledge-sharing efforts.

Methodology

This study employed a correlational design to examine the predictive strength of relationships. The self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data. The adapted questionnaire from Abdul-Rauf, Jabar and Mansor's (2020) research was modified to fit the area of this research. Cronbach's Alpha analysis of the instrument revealed an acceptable internal consistency of the items ($\alpha = 0.81$); types of social media $\alpha = 0.79$, use of social media $\alpha = 0.84$, influence of social media $\alpha = 0.80$, and challenges of social media $\alpha = 0.78$. Data were analyzed quantitatively using descriptive statistics and measures of dispersion to summarize the data, and Multiple

Regression Analysis was used to test the research hypotheses. The study systematically selected 2 federal university libraries, one from each of Nigeria's six geopolitical regions, for a total of 12 federal university libraries that served as the study's sample.

A total of Six Hundred and One (601) librarians obtained from the 12 selected federal university libraries served as the population of the study in the following proportion; University of Maiduguri library has 83, Federal University Gashua, Yobe 23, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria 106, Federal University Dutse 31, University of Jos 49, Federal University, Lokoja 16, University of Nigeria, Nsukka 74, Alex Ekwueme University, Ndufu-Alike 24, University of Ibadan 84, Federal University, Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State 24, University of Benin 59 and Federal University, Otuoke 28 librarians. Taro Yamane's (1967) table was used to determine the sample size of "240" librarians drawn proportionately from the twelve selected federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Results

Out of the 240 distributed questionnaires, 227 were completed, returned and found valid; 2.5% (6 questionnaires) were missing; and 2.9% (7 questionnaires) had incomplete data.

Research Objectives One: To identify the social media platforms used by librarians for knowledge sharing in federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 1: Types of social media platforms

S/N	Types of social media platforms	Response				Decision
		Using		Not Using		
1	Facebook: for the dissemination of a wide range of information	163	71.8%	64	28.2%	Relevant (163, 71.8%)
2	Virtual Events Platforms: Zoom and Microsoft Teams, host events and webinars	130	57.3%	97	42.7%	Relevant (130, 57.3%)
3	LinkedIn: connect with professionals, share research-related content with academics	110	48.5%	117	51.5%	Not Relevant (110, 48.5%)
4	WhatsApp: communicate with users through group chats and one-on-one interactions	152	67.0%	75	33.0%	Relevant (152, 67.0%)
5	Blogs: publish longer-form content, such as articles, book reviews, and guides	66	29.1%	161	70.9%	Not Relevant (66, 29.1%)
	Pinterest: curate and share visual resources, infographics, reading lists, and educational content	160	70.5%	67	29.5%	Relevant (160, 70.5%)
6	X: share quick updates, links to articles, and engage in real-time conversations	101	44.5%	126	55.5%	Not Relevant (101, 44.5%)
7	Instagram: for sharing visual content, library events, book displays and user interactions	174	76.7%	53	23.3%	Relevant (174, 76.7%)
8	YouTube: create and share tutorials, virtual tours and recorded exhibition events	111	48.9%	116	51.1%	Not Relevant (111, 48.9%)
10	Snapchat: share time-limited content, announcements for events	167	73.6%	60	26.4%	Relevant (167, 73.6%)
11	TikTok: engaging young researchers through short-form video content	107	47.1%	120	52.9%	Not Relevant (107, 47.1%)

The findings on the social media platforms used for knowledge sharing reveal important insights into how librarians in federal university libraries share knowledge and support users in the digital environment. The data shows that platforms such as Instagram (76.7%), Snapchat (73.6%), Facebook (71.8%), Pinterest (70.5%), and WhatsApp (67.0%) are the most commonly used tools. The finding aligns with the study's central problem, which highlights inconsistent adoption of technology and limited structured use of digital platforms in KM activities.

The moderate use of Zoom/Microsoft Teams (57.3%) indicates growing adoption of virtual events and webinars for knowledge dissemination and professional development. Professional and content-driven platforms like LinkedIn (48.5%), Blogs (29.1%), YouTube

(48.9%), Pinterest (44.5%), and TikTok (47.1%) are underutilized. The imbalance between high-use and low-use platforms according to the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) demonstrates that librarians rely more on informal, socially oriented tools than platforms designed for structured professional knowledge exchange. This explains the behavioral construct of UTAUT towards their perception with the technology.

Research Objective Two: To determine the extent of social media platforms as predictors of knowledge sharing among librarians in federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 2: Extent of Using Social Media for Knowledge Sharing

S/N	Influence of Using Social Media	High Extent	UD	Low Extent	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Showcase the library's contributions to the academic community and research value	171 (75.3%)	21 (9.3%)	35 (15.4%)	3.91	1.255	Accepted
2	Librarians use data from social media analysis to meet user needs	97 (42.8%)	53 (23.3%)	77 (33.9%)	3.15	1.335	Accepted
3	Analysis of user engagement and resource preferences	99 (43.6%)	42 (18.5%)	86 (37.9%)	3.05	1.427	Accepted
4	Share information about new acquisitions and research tips	145 (63.9%)	22 (9.7%)	60 (26.4%)	3.55	1.448	Accepted
5	Sharing updates and events,	148 (65.2%)	20 (8.8%)	59 (26.0%)	3.58	1.434	Accepted
6	Direct interactions with users to gather real-time feedback	181 (79.7%)	21 (9.3%)	25 (11.0%)	4.07	.956	Accepted
7	Promoting and hosting virtual events and workshops	163 (71.8%)	12 (5.3%)	52 (22.9%)	3.79	1.288	Accepted
8	Resource sharing	167 (73.5%)	26 (11.5%)	34 (15.0%)	3.94	1.037	Accepted
9	Sessions on information literacy	187 (82.4%)	40 (17.6%)	0 (0.0%)	4.24	.732	Accepted
	Total Mean Statistics	1,358 (66.5%)	257 (12.6%)	428 (20.9%)	3.71	.701	Significant

The findings in Table 2 examine the extent to which social media usage predicts knowledge sharing in the libraries under study. Using a minimum mean value criterion of 2.5 for acceptance, all factors analyzed were accepted as predictors of knowledge sharing. The low standard deviations indicate a relative consensus of opinions among respondents across different social media applications.

The factors of session on information literacy (Mean: 4.24, SD: 0.732), showcasing the library's contributions to the academic community and research value (Mean: 3.91, SD: 1.255) and sharing information about new acquisitions (Mean: 3.55, SD = 1.448) are highly rated by the respondents. The relatively low standard deviations indicate agreement among respondents. Using social media also predicts knowledge sharing through meeting

user needs (Mean: 3.15, SD: 1.335) and user statistics and preferences (Mean: 3.05, SD: 1.427), but the variability in responses mirrors divergent opinions. This expands the UTAUT constructs by confirming that social media is an essential tool for librarians to improve their performance through better service delivery and engagement. Service delivery and engagement are factors that determine technological adoption and use.

Research Objectives Three: To determine the challenges affecting the effective use of social media platforms for knowledge sharing in federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 3: Challenges Affecting the Use of Social Media

S/N	Types of social media platforms	Response				Decision
		Using		Not Using		
2	Tacit knowledge is not easily shared among colleagues through social media platforms	80	35.2%	147	64.8%	Not Relevant (80, 35.2%)
3	Lack of tolerance for those doing things in different ways	192	84.6%	35	15.4%	Relevant (192, 84.6%)

4	New ideas are less converted into practice for problem-solving	86	37.9%	141	62.1%	Not Relevant (86, 37.9%)
5	No encouragement of knowledge sharing	164	72.2%	63	27.8%	Relevant (164, 72.2%)
6	Lack of incentives and organizational culture	201	88.5%	26	11.5%	Relevant (201, 88.5%)
7	Insufficient best practices for knowledge sharing	191	84.1%	36	15.9%	Relevant (191, 84.1%)

The findings show that the most pressing challenges are organizational culture and insufficient support systems to enable effective knowledge sharing and utilization. A major challenge identified is the lack of relevant information regarding the type of social media to use (87.2%). The lack of tolerance for diverse approaches to problem-solving (84.6%) further demonstrates that rigid organizational cultures hinder creativity and innovation. Another critical barrier is the lack of incentives and a weak organizational culture (88.5%), as well as a lack of

encouragement from top management for knowledge sharing (72.2%), which significantly impedes knowledge sharing. Additionally, the lack of standardized knowledge-sharing procedures (84.1%) indicates a structural gap, insufficient sharing of tacit knowledge (35.2%) and limited conversion of new ideas into practice (37.9%) were not perceived as threats.

The Regression Analysis

Table 4: Model Summary Regression Analysis

Model Summary	Model Summary	Model Summary	Model Summary	Model Summary
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.881a	.776	.770	.41532
a. Predictors: (Constant), Types of Social Media and Utilization of Social Media Platforms				

The predictors (Types and utilization of social media platforms) have a significant positive relationship with the outcome variable, librarians' knowledge sharing (R-value: 0.881). The R Square value (R² = 0.776) indicates that the combined impact of application and use of social media accounts for about 77.6% of the variation in librarians' knowledge sharing. This showed that less than 23% of the variations were accounted for by other factors.

The use of social media platforms is an important predictor of librarians' knowledge sharing, as indicated by the high R-squared and adjusted R-squared values. The solid association between the predictors and knowledge sharing is indicated by the significant R-value of 0.881.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 5: Regression Analysis (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	69.857	3	23.286	134.998	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.181	117	.172		
	Total	90.038	120			
a. Dependent Variable: Enhanced Knowledge Sharing of Librarians for Service Delivery						
Predictors: Types of Social Media and Utilization of Social Media Platforms						

The result shows that the regression model was statistically significant ($F(3, 117) = 134.998, p = .000$). Since the significance value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the result indicates that the predictors jointly made a significant contribution to enhanced knowledge sharing among librarians. The ANOVA table further shows that the Regression Sum of Squares was 69.857, indicating that a substantial proportion of the variation in enhanced knowledge sharing among librarians was explained by the model's predictors. The high F-value (134.998) shows that the regression model had strong

explanatory power and was a good fit for predicting enhanced knowledge sharing among librarians.

The null hypothesis, which states that social media platform use does not significantly predict enhanced knowledge sharing among librarians, is rejected. This implies that the use of social media platforms is a significant predictor of knowledge sharing among librarians in Nigeria's federal university libraries.

Regression Analysis Coefficients

Table 4.12: Coefficients Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.571	.301		-1.895	.031
	Types of social media	.844	.102	.653	8.284	.000
	Influence of social media	.429	.111	.313	3.859	.000
	Challenges of social media	-.193	.083	-.117	-2.330	.022

a. Dependent Variable: Enhancing Knowledge Sharing of Librarians

The intercept constant (Constant: -0.571, $t = -1.895$, Sig. = 0.061) represents the predicted value for enhancing librarians' knowledge sharing when all independent variables are set to zero. The negative t-value (-1.895) suggests that the intercept is slightly below zero, but it is statistically significant ($p = 0.031$, which is just below the 0.05 threshold).

Predictor One: Types of Social Media

Types of social media present a positive coefficient ($B = 0.844, t = 8.284, \text{Sig.} = 0.000$), which means that an increase in the effective use of these platforms leads to an improvement in knowledge sharing. The t-value (8.284) is large and positive, indicating a strong effect. The significance level ($p = 0.000$) confirms that this result is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

The results indicate that the types of social media platforms such as Instagram (76.7%), Snapchat (73.6%), Facebook (71.8%), Pinterest (70.5%), and WhatsApp (67.0%), have a strong and positive influence on librarians' knowledge sharing. With a coefficient (B) of 0.844, this predictor has the highest impact among all variables in the model. This suggests that libraries that actively

engage in technology adoption (Performance Expectancy and Social Influence construct of UTAUT) will experience higher knowledge sharing among librarians.

Predictor Two: Influence of Using Social-Media Platforms

The use of social media platforms also presents a positive coefficient ($B = 0.429, t = 3.859, \text{Sig.} = 0.000$), indicating that higher use of social media platforms significantly enhances knowledge sharing. The t-value (3.859) shows a strong positive influence while the p-value (0.000) confirms statistical significance, meaning this relationship is highly reliable.

Librarians use social media platforms such as LinkedIn, WhatsApp, Facebook, and institutional repositories for knowledge-sharing, collaboration, and professional networking. However, the lack of formal integration of social media into KM strategies may limit its full potential.

Predictor Three: Challenges of Using Social Media

The challenging factors presented a negative coefficient ($B = -0.193, t = -2.330, \text{Sig.} =$

0.022), suggesting an inverse relationship, meaning that an increase in certain challenge is linked to a slight decline in knowledge sharing. This inverse relationship with knowledge sharing, as indicated by the negative coefficient (-0.193) and negative t-value (-2.330), reveals that any slight increase in the challenges of using social media there will be significant decrease in knowledge sharing of the librarians. Applying the assumptions of the UTAUT suggests that perceived behavioral control and institutional challenges play a vital role in knowledge sharing.

Discussion of Findings

Social networking sites such as Facebook, Pinterest, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp are frequently used for knowledge sharing. Ahmed et al. (2019) highlight these platforms as prominent for creating knowledge-sharing channels. Mladenović and Krajina (2020) also noted that social networking sites are widely used among librarians, facilitating the sharing of both tacit and explicit knowledge. This aligns with Gatiti (2021), who found Facebook and Twitter to be the most commonly used platforms for knowledge sharing, enhancing the ability to document and gather relevant knowledge. The current study supports this perspective, showing that social media platforms facilitate the exchange of various types of knowledge. The use of these platforms helps librarians share best practices, fostering a collaborative knowledge-sharing environment.

Social media eliminates temporal and spatial barriers, making it easier for librarians to share knowledge globally. Photo and video-sharing applications like YouTube and collaborative websites like Wikipedia are recognized for their role in KM processes. Panahi, Ghalavand, and Sedghi (2021) identify these tools as critical in facilitating various dimensions of KM, including knowledge creation and dissemination. The findings of Gatiti (2021) support this, with YouTube being among the top platforms used for knowledge sharing in libraries.

While microblogs and personal blogs are less widely used than other social media tools, they still play a significant role in knowledge sharing. Blogs and microblogs facilitate the sharing of updates, contributing to knowledge dissemination. This study corroborates the

findings of Mladenović and Krajina (2020) that social networking sites (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter) and content communities are more commonly used for knowledge sharing than microblogs and blogs. Mosha and Holmner (2019) found that social networking tools (Facebook, MySpace) are more widely used than professional networks (LinkedIn, Wikis, Blogs) among knowledge workers. This study corroborates their findings by highlighting the use of these platforms in university libraries for enhancing knowledge sharing. However, the study also found that tools like Microblogs, Google Mail and Google Drive are less utilized, aligning with Mosha and Holmner's observations.

The study, therefore, accepts both hypotheses and concludes that application and use of social media significantly enhance and predict librarians' knowledge sharing in Nigerian university libraries. The study provides strong statistical evidence supporting the positive impact of these predictors on librarians' professional outcomes.

Theoretical Implications of the Study

The study contributes to KM theories by establishing social media platform use as a significant predictor of knowledge sharing among librarians. It confirms that digital interaction tools support the creation and exchange of tacit and explicit knowledge, thereby extending the relevance of knowledge sharing theory to academic library environments.

Practical Implications of the Study

The findings imply that academic libraries can improve knowledge sharing by encouraging librarians to use social media platforms strategically. Platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, YouTube, and collaborative tools can enhance service delivery when supported by adequate technological infrastructure.

Conclusion

The study concluded that social media platforms play a significant role in enhancing knowledge sharing among librarians in Nigerian federal university libraries. The findings revealed that librarians frequently use social networking sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Pinterest, and Pinterest

to share professional knowledge and interact with colleagues and library users.

The study further concluded that social media platforms support both tacit and explicit knowledge sharing. The regression analysis also confirmed that the types and utilization of social media platforms significantly predicted enhanced knowledge sharing among librarians for service delivery. Application and use of social media platforms reduce time and distance barriers in knowledge sharing. The study concluded that the use of social media platforms is an important predictor of knowledge sharing among librarians in federal university libraries in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Academic libraries in Nigeria should encourage librarians to use social media platforms for knowledge sharing.
2. University library management should develop clear social media policies to guide the professional use of social media platforms among librarians.
3. Librarians should be trained regularly on the effective use of different social media tools for knowledge sharing.
4. University libraries should provide adequate technological infrastructure to support effective social media use.
5. Academic libraries should organize workshops and capacity-building programs on digital literacy.

Conflicts of Interest

No potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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